

Qiṣṣat Dhī al-Qarnayn

also known as “Qiṣṣat Dhulqarnayn”, “Islamic Legend of Alexander the Great”

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Entry tags: Islamic Traditions, Universal Chronicle, Hadith, Religious History, Ancient Novel, Text, Religious Group, Hispano-Islamic, Apocalyptic Literature

The Arabic Alexander Romance attributed to Abū ‘Abd al-Malik, which recounts the life and conquests of Alexander the Great. The work casts Alexander’s campaigns as a proselytizing mission bestowed upon him by God to bring monotheism to the most distant regions of the world. Part of the Western-Arabic Alexander tradition, the text is closely related to the *Aljamiado Rrekontamiento del rrey Ališandre* and the anonymous *Ḥadīth Dhī al-Qarnayn* edited by Garcia Gomez. As noted by Faustina Doufikar-Aerts, its extant isnads date much of the text to the latter-half of the 9th century, although Z. David Zuwiyya demonstrates further additions up to the mid-13th century. The text is also noteworthy for its potential use of a lost work of al-Mas’ūdī, the thirty-volume chronicle *Akhbār al-zamān*, as a major source. It has been edited and translated by Zuwiyya based on two extant manuscripts in Madrid: Real Academia de la Historia Colección Gayangos 61 and Biblioteca Nacional de Madrid ms. 5378. The narrative of the text is the result of centuries of syncretism between the broader Alexander Romance tradition and Islamic exegetical literature and Christo-Islamic universal chronicles. The phenomenon is attributable to Alexander’s early identification with the figure of Dhū al-Qarnayn in Qur’an 18:83-102, which is itself a retelling of the seventh-century Syriac Christian Alexander Legend as edited by E.A. Wallis Budge. The *Qiṣṣat Dhī al-Qarnayn* presents Alexander as a fully Islamicized prophet guided by the angel Zayāqīl (a corruption of Raphael) and whose campaigns are explicitly religious, instituting forced conversions to monotheism for all conquered peoples. After capturing the Persian empire of Darius III and the Indian kingdom of Porus, Alexander then moves on to mythological realms, converting people such as the Tārish who have the faces of dogs and the bodies of geese, etc. He eventually enters the Land of Darkness in search of the Fountain of Immortality but is forced to turn back. Upon his return, he does not die in Babylon, but in the Holy City of Jerusalem. Throughout the text, Alexander is also continually identified with Muhammad by presaging his accomplishments. For example, Alexander rides the flying al-Burāq, circles the Ka’bah, and smashes the idols found within the temples of those he converts.

Date Range: 850 CE - 1250 CE

Region: Al-Andalus

Region tags: al-Andalus

The Islamic Caliphate founded in the 8th c. Typically, also used to describe the Muslim controlled areas of the Iberian Peninsula.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Zuwiyya, Z. David. 2001. *Islamic Legends Concerning Alexander the Great*. New York: State

University of New York Press.

- Source 2: Doufikar-Aerts, Faustina. 2010. *Alexander Magnus Arabicus: A Survey of the Alexander Tradition through Seven Centuries: from Pseudo-Callisthenes to Šūrī*. Paris & Walpole, MA: Peeters.
- Source 3: Gomez, Garcia E. 1929. *Un texto occidental de la Leyenda de Alejandro*. Madrid: Institutio de Valencia.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/beitrgezurgesch00nlgoog>
- Source 1 Description: Nöldeke, Theodor. 1890. *Beiträge zur Geschichte des Alexanderromans*. Vienna.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/Budge1889TheHistoryOfAlexanderTheGreat.../page/n7/mode/2up>
- Source 1 Description: Budge, Ernest A. W. 1889. *The History of Alexander the Great, being the Syriac Version, edited from five manuscripts of the Pseudo-Callisthenes*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/lifeandexploits00budggoog/page/n12/mode/2up>
- Source 1 Description: Budge, Ernest A. W. 1896. *The Life and Exploits of Alexander the Great, being a series of translations of the Ethiopic histories of Alexander by the Pseudo-Callisthenes and other writers*. London: C.J. Clay and Sons.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Other textile: Parchment

Notes: Refers to Real Academia de la Historia Colección Gayangos 61 and Biblioteca Nacional de Madrid ms. 5378

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

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Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb
– No

↳ Cemetery
– No

↳ Temple
– No

↳ Shrine
– No

↳ Altar
– No

↳ Devotional marker
– No

↳ Cenotaph
– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The Real Academia de la Historia and Biblioteca Nacional de Madrid in Madrid, Spain

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

Notes: Text has many features of Maghrebi Middle Arabic.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: NA

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– No

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing or missionary work part of the historical culture of the community referenced in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– No

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?

– No

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?

– No

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force?

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– I don't know

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– I don't know

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– I don't know

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– I don't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: NA

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: Z. David Zuwiyya's Islamic Legends Concerning Alexander the Great contains an index and bibliography for the text

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: NA
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - No

- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: NA
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams
 - No
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices
 - No

↳ Only through religious specialists
– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch
– I don't know

↳ Other form of communication with living
– Yes

Notes: Alexander is guided by the angel Zayāqīl throughout the text

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?
– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: NA

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: NA

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: A number of mirabilia and marvelous peoples are described in the text.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– Yes

↳ Other

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– I don't know

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– I don't know

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– I don't know

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: NA

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– I don't know

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: NA

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

↳ At specified time in future

– No

- ↳ At unspecified time in near future
 - Yes
- ↳ At unspecified time in distant future
 - No
- ↳ At some other time [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: NA
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - I don't know

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– I don't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

DRAFT

– Other

Notes: Little is known concerning the provenance of the text's composition or potential commission of the manuscript, which survives in only one ms.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Theodor Nöldeke. Beiträge zur Geschichte des Alexanderromans. Vienna.

Reference: Garcia Gomez. Un texto occidental de la Leyenda de Alejandro. Institutio de Valencia.

Reference: Z. David Zuwiyya. Islamic Legends Concerning Alexander the Great. State University of New York.

Reference: Faustina Doufikar-Aerts. Alexander Magnus Arabicus: A Survey of the Alexander Tradition through Seven Centuries from Pseudo-Callisthenes to Şūrī. Peeters.

Reference: Tesei Tommaso. The prophecy of Dū-l-Qarnayn (Q 18:83-102) and the Origins of the Qur'ānic Corpus.

Reference: Kevin Van Bladel. The Alexander Legend in the Qur'ān 18:83-102.

Reference: Kevin Van Bladel. The Syriac Sources of the Early Arabic Narratives of Alexander.

Reference: E. A. Wallis Budge. The Life and Exploits of Alexander the Great. isbn: 9781462273492.

Reference: Richard Stoneman. *The Greek Alexander Romance*. Penguin UK. isbn: 9780141907116.

Reference: Z. David Zuwiyya. *A Companion to Alexander Literature in the Middle Ages*. BRILL. isbn: 9789004183452.

Reference: Richard Stoneman, Kyle Erickson, Ian Richard Netton. *The Alexander Romance in Persia and the East*. Barkhuis. isbn: 9789491431043.